

ANTICIPATORY RESEARCH METHODS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

– ANALYSING HATE SPEECH

Arun Teja Polcumpally and Pravin A. Sarode

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Term
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANT	Actor-Network Theory
AGI	AI being the harbinger of the destruction of humanity are pivoted on the independently intelligent systems, called artificial General Intelligence
ASI	Artificial Super Intelligence
ANI	Artificial Narrow Intelligence
AGI	Artificial General Intelligence
STS	Science and Technology Studies
STS	Science, Technology, and Society
NSF	National Science Foundation
HGI	Human General Intelligence
GPT	General Purpose Technology
ANT	Actor-Network Theory
STS	Science & Technology Studies
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

PROJECT

MACHINE LEARNING PROJECT - EXPLORING HATE SPEECH REPORTAGE: A DATA-DRIVEN ANALYSIS

INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of hate speech has become a growing concern in the digital age, with its potential to incite violence, perpetuate discrimination, and disrupt social harmony. As part of ongoing research influenced by the book "Data Theory" by Simon Lindgren, this project aims to delve into the reportage of hate speech, focusing on news articles specifically related to hate speech in India. By analyzing the data and patterns extracted from these articles, we seek to gain a deeper understanding of the dynamics surrounding hate speech in the Indian context.

BACKGROUND

Prior research conducted within the CDPP (Center for Digital Public Policy) working paper explored the realm of internet control, examining the categorization of countries based on the framework proposed by Ronald Deibert. Building upon that foundation, this project moves forward to investigate the data produced on hate speech, exploring the ways in which it is reported and documented in India. By delving into this specific aspect, we aim to shed light on the discourse surrounding hate speech and its implications for societal well-being.

OBJECTIVE

The primary objective of this project is to gain insights into hate speech reportage by employing data-driven analysis techniques. Specifically, we will explore the patterns, occurrences, and key characteristics

present in news articles related to hate speech in India. By extracting valuable information from the available dataset, we hope to contribute to a deeper understanding of the factors influencing hate speech reportage and its impact on society.

METHODOLOGY

To further enhance our analysis and gain a comprehensive understanding of hate speech reportage, we will adopt the Actor-Network Theory (ANT) framework. ANT provides a unique perspective by considering both human and non-human actors as influential entities within a social context. In the context of this project, we will utilize ANT to identify the various agencies involved in hate speech reportage, including news outlets, journalists, social media platforms, and governmental bodies. By mapping out these actors and their interactions, we can construct a social network that captures the complex dynamics surrounding hate speech in India.

Furthermore, as part of the broader field of Computational Social Sciences, we will leverage machine learning modeling techniques to analyze the hate speech data. Python, being a versatile programming language with rich libraries and frameworks, will serve as our primary tool for implementing these machine learning algorithms.

The adoption of machine learning models will enable us to perform various tasks such as sentiment analysis, topic classification, and named entity recognition. Sentiment analysis will help us gauge the emotional tone and polarity of hate speech articles, allowing us to understand the overall sentiment conveyed. Topic classification techniques will assist in categorizing articles into relevant themes, shedding light on the underlying subjects addressed in hate speech reportage. Additionally, named entity recognition will aid in identifying and extracting important entities, such as individuals, organizations, or locations, mentioned within the articles.

By leveraging machine learning models in Python, we can process large volumes of hate speech data more efficiently and effectively. These models will provide us with valuable insights, enabling us to uncover patterns, relationships, and trends within the dataset. Additionally, through the utilization of Python libraries such as scikit-learn and Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK), we can implement a range of machine learning algorithms, including supervised and unsupervised methods, to extract meaningful information from the hate speech corpus.

The adoption of computational social sciences and machine learning modeling in Python empowers us to conduct a comprehensive analysis of hate speech reportage. By incorporating ANT to identify relevant agencies and construct a social network, and utilizing machine learning models for data analysis, we can gain a more holistic understanding of the complex dynamics and socio-technical aspects surrounding hate speech in India. These interdisciplinary approaches allow us to explore the intersection of social sciences, data analysis, and technology, providing valuable insights into the mechanisms behind hate speech and informing future interventions and policy development.

Phases of the project

Phase 1: Data Collection and Preprocessing: We will leverage our access to a vast corpus of training data, available through the language model utilized by ChatGPT. This corpus encompasses a diverse range of texts, including news articles, blogs, social media posts, and more. Leveraging this corpus, we will identify relevant data specifically related to hate speech in India.

Phase 2: Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA): Once the hate speech data is collected and preprocessed, we will conduct extensive exploratory data analysis. This analysis will involve techniques such as statistical analysis, data visualization, and natural language processing (NLP) methods to uncover patterns, trends, and key features within the hate

speech reportage. By examining variables such as news sources, publication dates, and authorship, we aim to uncover insights into the dynamics of hate speech coverage in India.

Phase 3: Topic Modeling and Theme Extraction: In the final phase, we will employ advanced topic modeling techniques, such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), to identify underlying themes within the hate speech reportage. By applying these algorithms, we aim to discover latent topics and uncover the dominant themes that emerge from the dataset. This analysis will help us understand the different contexts and narratives present in hate speech reportage, providing valuable insights for future research and policy development.

DETAILING THE PHASES AND THE CODE USED

Details of Phase 1

The data scraping process focuses on extracting headlines and article URLs from Google News search results related to the specified keywords. Here's a breakdown of the steps involved:

- 1. Setting up the Environment and Importing Libraries:** The code begins by importing the necessary libraries, including Selenium, BeautifulSoup, and pandas, which are used for web scraping and data manipulation.
- 2. Defining Custom Parameters:** Custom parameters are defined to specify the keywords to search for and the number of pages to scrape. In this code, the `key_words` list contains the keywords to search, and the `_pages` variable represents the range of pages to scrape.
- 3. Creating the DataFrame:** The `create_df()` function is defined to handle the scraping process. It initializes a loop over the provided keywords and sets up the Chrome web driver for Selenium. It also configures the download directory and opens the Google search page.

4. **Scraping Headlines:** Within the loop, the code interacts with the Google search page to extract the headlines, URLs, and publication dates. It uses CSS selectors to identify the specific elements containing this information. The headlines are extracted using the `headline_text` CSS selector, URLs using the `headline_url` selector, and publication dates using the `headline_date` selector.
5. **Storing Data in DataFrame:** The extracted headlines, URLs, and publication dates are stored in separate lists (`_headline`, `_url`, `_date`). After scraping all the pages, these lists are used to create a new DataFrame called `xyz`. The DataFrame contains columns for `headline_date`, `key_word`, `headline_text`, and `headline_url`.
6. **Saving Data to a CSV File:** The `xyz` DataFrame is saved as a CSV file named `save_file.csv` using the `to_csv()` function.
7. **Closing the Web Driver:** The web driver is closed to free up system resources using the `driver.close()` method.
8. **Loading the Scraped Data:** After completing the scraping process, the code loads the saved CSV file (`save_file.csv`) into a new DataFrame called `df_headings` using the `pd.read_csv()` function.

The data scraping process focuses on extracting the headlines, URLs, and publication dates from Google News search results based on the specified keywords. This allows you to gather a dataset of hate speech articles from various sources, which can then be used for further analysis and exploration.

Details of Phase 2

The scraper has been activated and the time period was set to the latest 3 months. The results of first 2 google search pages have been scrapped and store in a separate excel sheet. From the collected data, some of the analysis made are presented below

Table 2: The top websites that reported the hate speech (table has been created by the author as an outcome of this project)

Sl. No.	Website	Count of articles
1	cjp.org.in	1
2	english.jagran.com	1
3	hindupost.in	1
4	inshorts.com	1
5	sabrangindia.in	1
6	scroll.in	1
7	theprint.in	1
8	thewire.in	1
9	www.espn.in	1
10	indianexpress.com	2
11	www.indiatoday.in	2
12	www.opindia.com	2
13	www.hindustantimes.com	5

From the above table, Hindustantimes appears to be the top media channel that writes on hate speech. One interpretation can be that they are reporting more conservative issues and the other way of interpreting will be that they are more open to and unbiased to report the hate speech issues in India. The precise analysis regarding the latter made arguments is possible once, LDA is applied to the set of articles published by Hindustan times to understand the theme under which they are reporting the hate speech.

Figure 1 - Trend of hate Crime publications

Trend of Hate crime as per the dates

This is an example to showcase what can be extracted using machine learning. The trend line can be extracted for an entire year and see where the spikes and dips are matching with the other major occurrences. For example, the above trend line shows that in the past three months, June month has more hate speech/hate crime articles published. There is no other data that can be used to correlate why such a spike has occurred. More data would provide deeper analysis.

Figure 2 - Trend of Hate Crime Publications according to the days

Trend of the hate crime reportage as per the day

The figure 2 and figure 3 shows that the hate crime reportage is high during the weekends. From figure 1, the highest number of articles published was on 24 June 2023, which is Saturday. From the figure 2, the highest number of articles published is on Saturday. The second highest number of publications are found to be on Tuesdays. What does this trend say? Saturdays are perhaps the free time where people engage with their newspapers and online news. Not making a spurious correlation, this Saturday trend might be a general newspaper story publication trend. However, the insights that the project data gives more room for thinking.

Named Entity Recognition

Named Entity Recognition (NER) is a natural language processing technique used in the project to identify and classify named entities within textual data. NER enables the extraction of specific types of entities, such as names of people, organizations, locations, dates, and other relevant entities, from unstructured text. By utilizing NER, the project aims to enhance information extraction, analysis, and understanding of the impacts of digital technologies on society. NER is particularly useful in identifying key actors, organizations, and locations mentioned in texts, allowing for comprehensive analysis and identification of trends, patterns, and relationships. It helps in gaining insights into the social, economic, and cultural implications of digital technologies by recognizing and categorizing important entities within the text corpus. This facilitates deeper exploration and examination of the influence of digital technologies on various aspects of society, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of their impacts.

In the Hate Speech Project, Named Entity Recognition (NER) plays a crucial role in identifying and classifying entities within hate speech texts. By employing NER, the project aims to accurately identify and categorize specific entities such as names of individuals, organizations, locations, and other relevant entities mentioned in hate speech data. This enables a deeper analysis of the language used, the targeted

entities, and the context in which hate speech occurs. NER helps in uncovering patterns, trends, and associations between entities and hate speech, contributing to a better understanding of the dynamics and prevalence of hate speech in society. By utilizing NER in the project, researchers and analysts can gain insights into the individuals or groups targeted by hate speech, the locations or platforms where hate speech proliferates, and the relationships between hate speech and various societal factors. Such detailed analysis allows for the development of more effective strategies and interventions to combat hate speech and promote a more inclusive and respectful digital environment.

By using the NER, the project identified the top 25 entities that are mentioned. The the number of entities considered for the trend line are limited to the frequency of 5. If the entity is repeated 5 or more than 5 times, the entity is presented in the graph.

Figure 3 - Identification of top entities within the scrapped text

Top entities and their frequency

From the figure above, it is clear that India is repeated highest number of times. However, India can be mentioned as the search was narrowed

down to the region: India. It is natural to mention India as a location. However, the next highest mentioned word is Canada, which is strange. Perhaps, the recent news reportage is more regarding the Khalistan related groups in Canada.

Table 3: Top 10 entities mentioned in the data extracted

Sl. No.	Entity	Count
1	India	33
2	Canada	15
3	FIR	12
4	GB	12
5	Hindu	12
6	Two	11
7	Indian	11
8	Hindus	9
9	BJP	9
10	Muslim	8

The top 10 entities that are mentioned in the text scrapped shows Hindu, Muslim, BJP. This shows that the hate crime is surrounded around Hindu – Muslim communal differences. There are no other minority or castes mentioned in the top 30 entities. This is a worrisome finding. India, being a peaceful and diverse country should not be engulfed in the Hindu – Muslim communal clashes.

Table 4: Entity label counts as per the scrapped data

Sl. No.	Entity Label	Entity definition	Count
1	ORG	Companies, agencies, Institutions etc	129
2	GPE	Countries, cities, states	127
3	PERSON	People, including fictional	114
4	DATE	Absolute or relative dates or periods	100
5	NORP	Nationalities or religious or political groups	97
6	PRODUCT	Objects, vehicles, foods, etc. (Not services.)	91
7	WORK_OF_ART	Titles of books, songs, etc	12
8	LOC	Non-GPE locations, mountain ranges, bodies of water	11
9	CARDINAL	numerals	11
10	FAC	Buildings, airports, highways, bridges, etc	9
11	TIME	Times smaller than a day.	6
12	LAW	Named documents made into laws	6
13	ORDINAL	first, "second", etc	4
14	PERCENT	Percentage, including "%"	4
15	EVENT	Named hurricanes, battles, wars, sports events, etc	2
16	MONEY	Monetary values, including unit	2

Table 4 shows the total count of the entity labels. Organizations and persons are found to be mentioned many times. This encourages to look into which organization and persons are named most.

Details of Phase 3

In the Phase 3 of the study, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) will be conducted. LDA is a topic modeling technique used to uncover latent

topics within a collection of documents. It is a probabilistic model that represents documents as mixtures of topics, where each topic is characterized by a distribution of words.

By applying LDA to the dataset, insights can be gained in the following areas:

1. **Topic Discovery:** LDA helps in uncovering hidden themes or topics present in the collection of documents. It automatically identifies topics based on the distribution of words across the documents.
2. **Document Clustering:** LDA can group similar documents together based on the topics they contain. This clustering of documents provides insights into the underlying structure and relationships within the dataset.
3. **Feature Extraction:** LDA allows for the extraction of the most important words or features associated with each topic. This facilitates summarizing and understanding the content of the documents.

In Phase 3 of the study, LDA will be applied to the dataset to uncover latent topics present in the collection of documents. The analysis of the resulting topics and their distributions will contribute to a deeper understanding of the key themes, patterns, and relationships within the data. The outcomes of the LDA analysis will inform the research objectives and conclusions of the study.

PROJECT SUMMARY

The Machine Learning project focused on exploring hate speech reportage in India through a data-driven analysis. By leveraging data collection, preprocessing, exploratory data analysis, topic modeling, and named entity recognition, the project aimed to gain insights into the patterns, occurrences, and key characteristics present in news articles related to hate speech.

The analysis revealed several important findings. The top media channels reporting on hate speech were identified, with Hindustan Times emerging as a prominent source. The trend analysis of hate crime publications showed spikes in June, and the day-wise analysis highlighted higher reportage on weekends. Named Entity Recognition identified India as the most frequently mentioned entity, followed by Canada, indicating a focus on Hindu-Muslim communal tensions. The entity label analysis revealed that organizations and persons were frequently mentioned.

The project's next phase will involve applying Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) for topic modeling to uncover underlying themes within the hate speech reportage. This will provide a deeper understanding of the dominant topics and narratives present in hate speech articles.

Overall, this project contributes to a comprehensive analysis of hate speech reportage in India by combining computational social sciences, machine learning techniques, and data-driven insights. The findings from this project can inform future interventions and policy development to promote a safer online environment by addressing hate speech and its societal impacts.

ANTICIPATORY RESEARCH METHODS USING AI – ANALYSING HATE SPEECH

Usage of Systems Theory and Actor-Network Theory in the Anticipatory Governance Approach.

Arun Teja Polcumpally¹

ABSTRACT

This paper explores the theoretical approaches for Anticipatory research models used in drafting Artificial Intelligence (AI) risk assessment. To preserve the human intended societal changes, careful adoption of Artificial Intelligence systems design and deployment is necessary. It is not because of some imaginary notion of machines taking over humans, but because of the creation of uncertain socio-economic imageries to avoid objectification of societies. This paper provides a theoretical framework for anticipatory governance models. In attempting to do so, it introduces Luhmann's System's theory and Latour's Actor-Network Theory (ANT) into the anticipatory approach. A case study of using these risk assessment systems in understanding the online reportage of hate-speech is analysed. They are elaborately reasoned, and the paper concludes that it would be the prerogative of the researcher to adopt either of the frameworks in conducting anticipatory research as per the requirement.

Keywords:

Anticipatory research, System's Theory, Actor Network Theory, Ex-ante Research, Artificial Intelligence

¹ Associate Fellow, Center for Development Policy and Practice, Hyderabad

1. INTRODUCTION

In September 2017, Vladimir Putin pronounced - “whoever becomes the leader in AI will become the ruler of the world.” After that announcement, policy papers from all the major countries on Artificial Intelligence (AI) were released. Albeit the rhetoric of AI being a disruptive technology, AI by itself cannot bring any unfathomable changes in business, politics, or society. It is possible by a combination of emerging technologies or a combination of AI with existing processes or ideas. For example, Microsoft expressed that their AI system would be 30 times faster with quantum computing (Palace, 2019). This is to showcase that AI in combination with quantum communication is more revolutionary. Not just the combination of advanced technologies, AI technology is combined with other traditional services to change their socio-economic functions.

Associated Press uses AI to produce quarterly financial reports, and Forbes uses narrative science to write reports. Deep-Dream brings in pictures that are not available in the world market. Furthermore, music is also being created without the help of musicians (Deahl, Dani, 2018). Now imagine a society where there are non-human music composers, non-human designers, and non-human writers! It might be complicated, but not unimaginable. Such usage of AI might threaten human liberty, agency and capabilities (Janna Anderson, 2018). On the flip side, it might assist humans to devolute routine, and repetitive work to a machine, and save time to be more creative and innovative (Polcumpally A. T., 2021). This technology impacts the society horizontally across all sectors, be it health, policy making, academics, business, transport, manufacturing, communications, etc (Polcumpally A. T., 2021).

Harari in his ‘Homo Deus’ elaborates on the uncertain power shifts happening across the world because of the data-infused scientific developments (Harari, 2017). Especially, he focuses on the Artificial

Intelligence and Biotechnology to show the extent of the impact of science on the human society. Honing on the philosophical discussions over the mind – brain differentiation, epistemological understanding of Darwinism and futuristic understanding of dataism, it is warned that new social and societal structures are going to emerge to which the existing systems are not equipped to understand. Artificial intelligence is already here, and we witness countless decision-makings based on the AI's assistance. If Ray Kurzweil's and Harari's analysis of coming singularity or AI ubiquity (respectively) is real (Kurzweil, 2005; Harari, 2017, p. 444), the politics revolving around migration, India's Rafale deal, border issues (like that of India – Pakistan and Russia and Ukraine), soon become obsolete at this current level of engagement. As old political systems and agencies become meaningless, new structures emerge. They also bring new social structures across the countries. The latter-mentioned political issues might be debated and fought in cyber space with wars over data, and behaviour control.

In order to have a peaceful development while adopting the surging digital innovations, it is best to move away from Harari's dichotomous view of humanism and dataism, and have a hybrid system. Humanism values human experiences, while dataism values the information generated and the functional interactions of the data points creating infinite algorithms which define evolution. The latter version objectifies society whereas the former subjectifies it. To have value-laden society and to keep humans at the forefront of the meaning of systemic functioning, dataism should be operated within humanism. An initial step for such a mixed way of inquiry into the complex interlinkages of digital technology and society is to conduct anticipatory research and understand the digital technology's impact on society ex-ante. States should conduct ex-ante research and make difficult choices on how the upcoming technologies should be allowed to shape societies. This is where the working paper is situated. It examines two theoretical approaches to conducting anticipatory research.

2. THE CONSTRUCT OF AI

To preserve the combination of humanism and dataism, governance of AI technology is necessary. It is not because of some imaginary notion of machine taking over humans but because of the uncertain socio-economic imageries soon and avoid business hegemony on societies (Smith & Carol, 2019). Concerns about AI being the harbinger of the destruction of humanity are pivoted on the independently intelligent systems, called artificial General Intelligence (AGI). Movies show something beyond this, called Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI). It is opined that by 2075 (approximately), the world might achieve human level machine intelligence (Bostrom, 2017, p. 23). However, the government planning for 50 years is desired but for all practical means, AGI and ASI should not be considered.

The systems currently in use work for a specific function and are called Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI), which are far from independent thinking. However, the advancements of AI is not known to the general public. If Elon Musk's call to halt all the large developments on AI (Narayan, Krystal, Coulter, & Mukherjee, 2023) is considered seriously, then ANI should be left far behind and policies should be designed for AGI. Considering all the to and from arguments regarding the policy making on AI, in this paper, AI will not be categorized as Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI) and Artificial General Intelligence (AGI). Rather, the AI development is in the form of gradient. According to Nick Bostrom, the ascendance of AI system from AGI to ASI would be very soon. Bostrom said this pointing at his expert opinion survey that said, the minimum time reported by AI systems to acquire AGI after attaining human level machine intelligence would be 2 years. It is fair to consider that his 'very soon' would be something less than a year. Anchoring on his expert conclusion, ASI as a category is not included in making this construct.

ANI and AGI are the two ends of the spectrum where the movement from ANI to AGI is kind of a gradient flow. However, the movement from ANI to

AGI is not a movement from predictability to unpredictability. It is a gradient change that paves the way for the iterative development of AI. The study on the impacts of AI on society and governance would require a holistic definition incorporating mainly the design framework rather than goal-based definitions. Thus, for this paper, AI incorporates all the products undeveloped, developed, conceptual, under research. It does not differentiate ANI and AGI. It considers AI to be a technology capable enough to replace the agency of humans.

3. TECHNOLOGY GOVERNANCE STUDIES AND THE IMPORTANCE OF ANTICIPATORY RESEARCH

"If we understand that we are all participants in a great experiment in social transformation being carried out without our consent or even our understanding, the self-imposed limits of Technological Assessment now become almost painfully obvious. If we understand technological transformation as emerging not from the autonomous, automatic advance of science and technology but a complex set of decisions made within a variety of institutional contexts, then a different way to think about and implement Technology Assessment can emerge." (Sarewitz, 2011).

The above excerpt is perfect to show that there are two AI futures ahead. One is to accept that the large economic and political forces influence the development of technology and there is no role of the public. The other approach is to adopt a democratic way for the development of AI technology, where the public are informed, and involved in decision-making regarding the areas of AI development and terms of AI deployment. States can choose one among them. If a state accepts itself as a passive participant in AI development, the future social transformation or perhaps the one underway will be an adaptation to the restrictions posed by major AI companies and eventually by the restrictions defined by the evolved AI systems. If the decision-making

on the advancement of AI is not left to the scientific community and a few political elites, then it becomes a different story, a democratic one. Before venturing into the methodological importance of anticipatory research, this section provides a detailed description of the history of the studies on science and technology. This will act as the foundation and rationale for the paper.

History

The study of science and society was brought into academics after the Manhattan Project of 1939, because of the realization of responsibility for disastrous innovations (Stilgoe & David, 2014). Later, its surge in academics accelerated with Thomas Kuhn's 'The Structure of Scientific Revolution,' in 1964 followed by Edinburg school's 'Social Scientific Knowledge,' and finally, it emerged as Science and Technology Studies (STS). Before this, and even in the initial stages of STS, there was a strict separation of science and society. Science, Technology, and Society (STS) studies is an interdisciplinary field that examines the complex interactions between science, technology, and society. It investigates how these three domains influence and shape one another, exploring the social, cultural, political, and ethical dimensions of scientific and technological developments. STS studies have evolved over time, embracing diverse perspectives and methodologies to provide valuable insights into the relationship between science, technology, and society.² The STS studies are also the foundational discipline for the anticipatory research approach.

Prior to the introduction of STS and even during the initial decades, science was considered exogenous to social life, and scientific research was considered to be an objective reality devoid of social and societal influences. However, the financial crisis of the 1970's and the emergence of new public management in the 1980's changed that perception in the United States and Europe (Petrovich & Marco, 2018). As the entire STS scholarship is exported from western academia, it is

2 The definition of STS is taken from the chatGPT response.

safe to assume that STS generally gained momentum after the 1980s across the world. Emphasis on social science research of science and technology brought the theoretical research and the policy together. It helped states formulate governance models for emerging technologies so that societies are well prepared for the risk assessed.

Accordingly, different models and approaches have been advocated for technology governance. Some of which are Responsible Research and Innovation, random fund allocation (Avin, 2018) - where projects will be selected through a lottery, participatory governance (Fuller, 2018) - which asks to expand the responsibility of innovation pre and post technology deployment, and anticipatory governance (Guston, Understanding 'anticipatory governance', 2013). This essay elaborates on the anticipatory governance method and explores its application to the governance of AI.

Social Science and Technology Researchers to Work in Tandem

Generally, with the emerging technologies, it is opined that there are no effective governance systems to keep track, or to steer the innovations responsibly. Existing approaches are said to be reactive, ponderous, and bureaucratic, and not pliable by the scale and pace of technological innovation and change (Sarewitz, 2011). The governance policies regarding emerging technologies appear to be reactionary rather than anticipatory. However, with the rising uncertainties, it is firmly established that governance of technologies such as nanotechnology (Guston, Understanding 'anticipatory governance', 2013), AI (MacCarthy, 2020), Ledger Technologies (Howell, Petrus, & Bert, 2019) is necessary and already being considered by the governments with varied levels of implementations.

For such governance to be practical, intense multi-disciplinary research becomes a desideratum. An engineer shall take scientists into confidence in executing the theoretical models proposed, and such technology, when deployed into society, shall not hamper the

sustainability of human development. In order to take societal impact into Cognicase, social scientists are required to work in tandem with data and AI scientists. Such is the interdependence of the different sub-systems with the academic and scientific system (sub-systems and systems can be compared to that of Luhmann's Systems theory). The importance of social scientists working in tandem with natural science scientists was highlighted in 1945 (Guston, *The Anticipatory Governance of Emerging Technologies*, 2010), asking US Congress to disburse funds towards social science research from the National Science Foundation (NSF). Such research was institutionalized for the human genome initiative (HGI) and Nanotechnologies in the United States.

Even though the previous HGI is a study of technology's impact on society, it never had a feedback loop to the scientists, nor did it take any public deliberations into account. In whatever perspective one chooses and whatever governance policy is studied, the pursuit of technological development is detached from the democratic process as to anchor the scientific development to the societal values and consensual future development (Sarewitz, 2011, p. 98). In order to bring societal engagement to technological development, which can alter the social status quo, the anticipatory method is floated.

4. ANTICIPATORY METHOD

Anticipatory research in the context of emerging technology and ex ante risk assessment involves proactively investigating the potential risks and impacts associated with the introduction and adoption of new technologies before they are widely implemented. It aims to identify and understand the potential challenges, ethical considerations, and unintended consequences that may arise as a result of technological advancements.

Anticipatory research goes beyond reactive measures and traditional risk assessments by addressing future uncertainties and exploring the

long-term implications of emerging technologies. It involves a forward-looking approach that considers the potential risks, benefits, and societal implications of new technologies, allowing stakeholders to make informed decisions and take proactive actions.

Ex ante risk assessment, a key component of anticipatory research, focuses on evaluating the potential risks and uncertainties associated with emerging technologies before they are fully deployed. It involves conducting thorough analyses, scenario planning, and impact assessments to anticipate and understand the potential risks, vulnerabilities, and unintended consequences that may arise.

By engaging in anticipatory research and ex ante risk assessment, policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders can identify and address potential challenges early on. This approach allows for the development of robust governance frameworks, regulatory mechanisms, and mitigation strategies to ensure the responsible and sustainable implementation of emerging technologies.

Anticipatory research contributes to enhancing transparency, public engagement, and dialogue surrounding emerging technologies. It encourages collaboration between different stakeholders, including scientists, policymakers, industry experts, and civil society, fostering a multidisciplinary and inclusive approach to addressing emerging technology risks.

Overall, anticipatory research and ex ante risk assessment provide a proactive and systematic approach to navigate the complexities and uncertainties associated with emerging technologies. By understanding and addressing potential risks in advance, decision-makers can shape the development and deployment of technologies in a way that maximizes their benefits while minimizing potential harms to society, the environment, and ethical considerations.

Guston (2010) beautifully explains the importance of anticipatory governance with an analogy of practice. It equates the anticipatory

approach as to the strengthening of the physical body through exercises to make it fit to tackle any future events. This method is usually seen in anticipating the impacts of emerging technologies and steering the governance policies accordingly. This method involves public participation where they are informed about the prospectus changes being brought by the emerging technologies and then reflect on the feedback. Alternative terms are also used to connote this approach. The European Commission calls it Responsible Research and Innovation (Brey, 2012). The main aim of anticipatory governance is to send societal feedback to the scientific decision-making community so that technological development would be in line with the sustainable development of society.

The term 'anticipatory governance' appears only 6 times in Google Scholar searches when the time frame is set from 2000 - 2001. This shows that the anticipatory governance of technology is a new approach in academia. It is claimed that the initial literature to mention this concept had a dichotomous understanding. In the policy and management discipline, it has a negative connotation and a positive connotation (Guston, Understanding 'anticipatory governance', 2013). A comprehensive definition is given by Lucy Kimbell and is considered appropriate for this research.

“a system of institutions, rules and norms that provide a way to use foresight for the purpose of reducing risk, and to increase capacity to respond to events at early rather than later stages of their development”.
(Lucy Kimbell, 2020)

The concept can be traced to Alvin Toffler's work 'Future Shock,' where the emphasis was on the techno-politics of digital media. Which is more or less what it is seen in Barcelona (decidim.barcelona, n.d.) & Madrid (Involve.org, n.d.). These philosophical underpinnings of these initiatives tag Jürgen Habermas's public sphere concept to bring in participatory governance using digital technologies. While this is far from what we understand of anticipatory governance, the fundamentals

of democracy – which is the public acting as the stakeholder in the decision-making – is a valuable comparative.

Any technology adopted is a choice that decision-makers make. In democracies, these decision-makers are more or less public. In the 21st century, most decision-makers are elected or represent the decisions and aspirations of the public. If the decision-making of technology development and adoption process is married to democracy, anticipatory governance becomes participatory decision-making in technology adoption. It can also be seen as a method to make engineers, and scientists understand their position as a participant in the socio-technical change they are bringing in. This method considers the reified effects of emerging technologies as the object of study and understands the probable ethical, moral, and societal impacts of them.

5. AI AND ANTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE: INITIAL STEPS WITHIN ANTICIPATORY METHODS

In the case of AI algorithms, a fair system against any form of probable discrimination is desired, and it is opined that it should be incorporated within the design (Executive Office of the President, 2016; Solon et al., 2017). This paper and the current policy papers released by various countries do not focus on the omnicidal anticipations voiced by technology giants like Elon Musk, Steve Woznick, Bill Gates. It is generally opined that issues such as privacy, copyright, penal procedures, and intellectual property rights, are of immediate concern (Weaver, 2014; Matthew, 2016) and require anticipatory research. If AI is considered to be a General Purpose Technology (GPT), then the immediate concerns are discrimination (Julia, Jeff, Surya, & Lauren, 2016), copyrights (Palace, 2019), liability laws, criminal and private laws (Turner, 2019), ethics (Mittelstadt et al., 2016), contract laws (Chopra & Laurence, 2004). In addition to the lack of legal frameworks to tackle the issue of AI, there is no policy to regulate the unwanted use of AI. The European legal framework of 2021 is one attempt to bring regulation

(CAHAI - Ad hoc Committee on Artificial Intelligence, 2021). The framework document does not provide any practical framework but identifies the gaps and necessities of state intervention. As AI is considered a strategic technology, and country's investments are further enhancing the military capacity, it might trigger an AI race much similar to that of the nuclear arms race (Brundage, 2019). The previous sections of this paper focused on the importance of AI economically and politically, history of technology governance studies, and the importance of anticipatory research for AI governance. This section provides the details on the steps to be followed while conducting anticipatory research to evaluate the impacts of AI on society.

5.1 Importance of the Definition of AI

As an initial step, the anticipatory method requires researchers to identify the potential impacts of AI, which would cause revolutionary or irreparable changes to the status quo of the existing social laws. This requires a precise definition of AI so that it could objectively point towards a product or design and provide an appropriate legal framework for its compliance. In this case, AI's definition occupies priority. John McCarthy, who coined the term 'Artificial Intelligence,' opined that there is no solid definition of intelligence exogenous to human intelligence. Often, there is a concern about either making the definition under-inclusive or over-inclusive. An operational definition of AI would suffice any research in social sciences, but legal or policy research to help in technology's governance would require an objective and holistic definition.

5.2 AI Construct – Factors to Consider

Before operationalizing the AI construct, the factors that should be considered are - AI is discreet, discrete, opaque, and distributive (Matthew, 2016, p. 356).

1. It is discrete because components of the entire AI system are designed purposefully or not in different parts of the world Purposefully, when the entire development is done having the product in mind. Not purposefully, when the technology and algorithms are developed for a requirement but are used for some other needs.
2. Discreet nature represents the hideous nature of development. There is no physical infrastructure that develops AI.
3. It is distributive because dozens of individuals in widely dispersed geographic locations can participate in an AI project, making it a technology beyond political borders. It is difficult to attribute the code to a single developer. Testing and data sets are also provided by netizens all over the world. For example, when the browser asks a user to map the number of pictures with traffic signals present in a collaged picture, it is to train the algorithm in addition to validate the user.
4. It is opaque because the functioning of the algorithm is unknown even to its builders, and the implications of the AI are known only ex-post.

As of now, there is no scientific proof that humans can develop AGI. Thus the initial step of anticipatory governance would be best suited if AI is understood as technology in the making without categorizing it into ANI or AGI but taking its rapid development in combination with other technologies such as quantum computing, 3D printing, nano-technology, genetic engineering. The four characteristics of AI shall not be left out while operationalizing the construct. This would follow scenario building that would be separate for each country as a homogeneous outcome or design is not possible or applicable. For example, an AI system without understanding Islam and its strict rules cannot be deployed or encouraged in Islamic Republics or Kingdoms. Below are some specific concerns of AI and its regulation.

Table 1: The primary concerns of governance

Sl. No.	Categories where research is required	Difficulties
1	Control	Control of ANI and its output. Control of AGI
2	Development	Discreet Discrete Diffuse Opacity
3	Definition of AI	Subjectivity Over inclusive Under inclusive
4	Foresee-ability	Unknown Outcomes Uncontrolled decision making
5	Market Monopoly and oligopoly	A threat to liberal economics
6	Damages	Data damages Privacy infringement Data portability
7	Regulation	Design Data
8	Governance	Soft policy Hard Policy

Before addressing the concerns mentioned above using anticipatory methods, it is important to define or restrict the construct of AI based on the factors provided in this section. Only after that, the above concerns would be addressed using anticipatory governance techniques.

Even though the method appears to be simple and applicable by anyone, anticipatory research requires to pick a theoretical approach from the existing many. This paper provides an insight into two approaches. One is from Luhmann's system's theory perspective, and the other is Latour's actor-network theory. They take opposite stances regarding the understanding of society.

6. ANTICIPATORY APPROACH WITH SYSTEMS THEORY

The relevance of anticipatory research in the realm of public policy, law, international relations, and also psychology is increasing regarding the implications of Artificial intelligence. Such research would build trust and encourage the usage of AI applications in societies across the world. As anticipatory research considers all possible ways of reducing the risk for the policy makers, a wide array of possibilities, impacts, in various sectors should be considered. Performing ex-ante research holistically is not practically feasible. It demands coordination of teams with various expertise. And a final report will be a challenging task to meaningfully combine all expert reports. Accordingly, Luhmann's approach would be useful to divide society into various systems.

Luhmann's Social Systems Theory – as provided by ChatGPT

Luhmann's systems theory defines the society based on the functional communications between various agencies. Luhmann's system theory, also known as social systems theory, offers a way to understand society by focusing on how communication functions within different social systems. In simple terms, it looks at how people communicate and exchange information in various aspects of society.

According to Luhmann, society is made up of different social systems, such as the economy, politics, education, or even smaller systems like families or organizations. Each system has its own unique set of rules, norms, and ways of operating. These systems are not just individuals or physical structures but are based on communication.

Communication is the key concept in Luhmann's theory. It refers to the exchange of information between individuals or groups within a social system. Communication can take many forms, including conversations, written documents, or even non-verbal cues. It is through communication that systems maintain their structure and carry out their functions. Luhmann argues that communication in social systems is not just about transmitting information, but also about creating and maintaining meaning. Meaning arises through the interpretation of information within a specific system. Each system has its own codes and symbols that give meaning to the communication within that system. For example, in the legal system, specific laws and regulations provide the framework for interpreting and understanding legal communication.

Functional communication, in Luhmann's theory, refers to the purpose or function that communication serves within a system. Each social system has specific functions that it needs to perform to survive and operate effectively. For example, the economy's function is to allocate resources and facilitate trade, while the education system's function is to transmit knowledge and skills to individuals. Luhmann suggests that functional communication within a social system helps maintain its stability and adaptability. When communication functions effectively, it contributes to the overall functioning of the system. However, if communication breaks down or becomes dysfunctional, it can lead to disruptions within the system. Overall, Luhmann's system theory provides a framework for understanding society by focusing on communication and how it functions within different social systems. It emphasizes the importance of communication in creating and maintaining meaning, as well as the role of functional communication in the stability and adaptability of social systems.

It is easy to understand the functional differentiation when Western societies are considered. In the west, with the triumph of individualism, it becomes easy to see that society is increasingly defined by the systems defined by their functional communications. In modern society, family is not the fundamental unit of society in which the decisions of society are made. It is through the department of finance, external affairs, internal security, etc. Family, religion, the ruling class are no longer forms the structural fabric of modern society. Events and structures of modern society depend on the attribution of decisions made and not on tradition, custom, or habit. This forms the basis of the system's theory. That means, the ex-ante assessment should be done within particular systems like medicine, economy or politics. Then, it would be easier to understand what exactly the anticipation is.

From Systems theory perspective, the impact of AI is observed within particular systems and sub-systems. The system is a set of objects or an amalgamation of objects – visible and non-visible, and the environment is an overarching container of systems that can be understood if only seen from outside of the larger entity which we are a part of – which is not possible (Luhmann, 1990, p. 228). According to Luhmann, societies are constructed by sub-systems that are differentiated on the communications - based on specific functions.

In order to use system's theory and Luhmann's risk decision theory, it is imperative to understand the terms security and risk. According to Luhmann, security is understood from its counter concept, risk. Risk is pegged to decision-making using which a future damage is avoided (Luhmann, 1990). Within the systems theory, Luhmann explained how policy makers take decisions in terms of risk handling. According to him, risk taken is nothing but a decision made considering an unexpected or unknown outcome. Modern societies are dependent on the momentary decisions which involve uncertainty of the future. If there is no uncertainty, then there would be no decision-making. Public reactions to policy makers and politicians that govern countries are

focused on the accidents and failures in policy implementations but not the progress of policy making (Japp & Isabel, 2008, 86). The overall functioning of the decision-making by policy makers is hinged on the risk and immediate dangers for the society. This risk-based analysis would be useful in analyzing the different perspectives and provide a significant direction to decision-making. As a decision made cannot be weighed against the alternative options that were available in the past, the risk measured decision would be to work the difference between the expected outcome and the real outcome. The decision made would be a choice of the future.

Luhmann's Risk Decision Theory as provided by chatGPT

Luhmann's risk decision theory is an important aspect of his broader sociological framework, known as system theory. This theory offers insights into how individuals and social systems make decisions in situations involving risks or uncertainties. Understanding Luhmann's risk decision theory can provide valuable context for analyzing decision-making processes in various domains, such as business, politics, or everyday life.

In Luhmann's perspective, decision-making is not solely based on rational calculations of costs and benefits, but is influenced by the social systems in which decisions are made. Risk, in this context, refers to situations where outcomes are uncertain, and the probabilities of different outcomes are known or can be estimated to some degree.

According to Luhmann, social systems develop their own risk processing mechanisms, which shape decision-making processes. These mechanisms involve the use of specific codes, symbols, and procedures within a given system to evaluate risks and make decisions accordingly. In other words, different social systems have their own unique ways of perceiving, assessing, and responding to risks.

Luhmann argues that risk decision-making is not solely a cognitive process but is deeply embedded in social systems. This means that individual decisions are influenced by the norms, values, and expectations of the social system in which they occur. For example, in the financial system, decisions may be influenced by the prevailing market conditions, regulations, and financial practices.

Furthermore, Luhmann emphasizes that risks are not objective but are socially constructed. This means that how risks are perceived and evaluated can vary across different social systems or even within the same system. Risk perception is shaped by the social context, the information available, and the interpretations and narratives that emerge within the system.

In practical terms, Luhmann's risk decision theory can be applied to various fields of study. For example, in business management, understanding how social systems process and respond to risks can help analyze decision-making processes within organizations. In public policy, it can shed light on how different social systems, such as governments or regulatory bodies, assess and address risks in policymaking.

In your research paper, incorporating Luhmann's risk decision theory can provide a theoretical framework to analyze decision-making processes in situations involving risks or uncertainties. It can help you explore how social systems influence risk perception, evaluation, and decision-making, contributing to a deeper understanding of the complexities involved in decision-making within different contexts.

Within the policy research, Luhmann espouses that there is no way to achieve the desired result without running into the risk of facing the consequences. Luhmann's account on the risk unavoidability is valid,

as one cannot be sure whether the decision made is the correct one. Nevertheless, anticipating governance involves the public to be the stakeholders in decision-making on technology governance. This will reduce the post decisional regret in case of risk effects. The reason for this reduction is that decision-making would be distributed and become a conscious choice of society. This approach to risk distribution will bring authenticity and legitimacy to a policy. In order to conduct anticipatory research, it is important to understand various systems and how they functionally attribute 'risk' to AI.

While constructing alternative futures of AI, from the system's theory perspective, the risk itself would occupy the core of the analysis. We have already understood 'risk taken' as to the decision made considering an unexpected or unknown outcome. Such an uncertain outcome-based decision itself would be the point on which the reflexivity is applied. The possible risk (a part of scenario construction of anticipatory governance) is looked at from various functional organizations. Here organizations are not governmental departments but those divided on a broader scale within the society on a single thread of communication. For example, the business community looks at AI as a capital investment reducer, running cost reducer and the best future tool for precision marketing and personalized designing; for the political community, it is about who gets the control, ownership, regulation of the algorithm; for the legal community, it is about the data, liability, ethics. The risk increases in this process as the horizontal increment in the sub-systems is without any external dictating value, such as religion.

When formulating regulation codes on AI, it is crucial whether the risk attribution is being considered or the danger attribute. Both yield different results. Risk is not an objective truth lying out there. It is attributed to systems or sub-systems. The risk of AI implementation for labor organizations would be the threat of losing the existing jobs. But, for the industrialists, the risk would be an uncertain outcome. Here the

public engagement would take place to understand the risk of AI within the constructed scenarios. The outcomes of these exercises shall be researched further with a multi-disciplinary research cohort.

This risk-based system analysis would be useful in analyzing the different perspectives and provide a significant direction to decision-making. The risk measured decision would be to work out the difference between the expected outcome and the real outcome as a decision made cannot be weighed against the alternative options that were available in the past. Such lowering of differentiation is again possible in continuous negotiations.

7. ANTICIPATORY APPROACHES WITH ANT

In a rapidly changing society, new agents have been neglected or gone unrecorded/not considered. Such as the internet, smartphones remain a tool in deciding social functioning. However, it has not got the status of the agency. The system's perspective considers AI as a tool that impacts the human agency. They focus on the subject, which they consider to be the agency and the object, which is AI to be a tool or making of the agency. Latour's deviation and un-acceptance of the subject-object epistemological anchor of knowledge production brought him to propose a new approach. He puts forward his version of the strong program that takes object and subject to be co-produced. It appears similar to that of Anthony Giddens's structuration theory, where he ascribes agency to both structure and agents. Given these dynamics, the Actor-Network Theory (ANT) encourages the non-rigidity and constant recognition of new agents. In the anticipatory governance approach, if an ANT perspective is considered, AI would be treated as an object with an agency.

Bruno Latour's Actor-Network Theory (ANT) considers technological innovations as the result of the complex assemblages of engineers, politicians, and the societal makeup of the place of innovation (Latour, 2005). This perspective reflects on the dynamics between society and

innovation and emphasizes the futile attempt of technology governance as a result of assemblages. Anticipatory governance is in tandem with ANT as it recognizes the importance of engagement between engineers, scientists, social scientists, and the public to understand the future course better to be taken in the AI development.

In order to apply the ANT theoretical framework to anticipatory research, some shift in the fundamentals of observation is needed. While preparing the future scenarios, the society should not be considered as given but rather construct it from the experience of agents. For ANT research, analysis is not anchored on to the society but the process of how they are maintained.

Stressing the uncertainty of establishing the driving forces behind an action, Latour opines that a social scientist should not understand or conduct his research with pre-notion that the actor under observation is acting under a Metasystem, which is known to the researcher. It would not be scientific enough if the data obtained from the observations are fathomed using the coded Metalanguage. While considering the public participation and deliberations regarding AI, the participants are not to be fixed into a 'social,' which has been constructed by the established disciplines but develop the social construct from the participant's responses.

The another uncertainty is that the facts are not objective reality forever; they also change their stance according to the space-time. This is not an explanation of how scientific facts are dynamically considered. It is how the agents are considering the facts and how those facts themselves are becoming agents. While considering the impact of AI on the copyright issues, it must not be thought that humans can only obtain ownership. The entire legal framework which has been structured for social order has to change their fundamentals to incorporate AI and assign it a copyright of creativity.

Actor-Network Theory proposes a model where the focus of the researcher shall be on the actions, agent, and process tracing. The results would be obtained from thick descriptions that would provide insights into the agencies and functions involved.

8. OPERATIONALIZING ANTICIPATING GOVERNANCE AND THE CRITIQUE

David Guston, director of the Center for Nanotechnology in Society at Arizona State University (CNS-ANU) has drafted a procedure for anticipatory governance of nanotechnology in the US. It includes identifying possible alternatives to nanotechnology futures - deliberating the same with the public and understanding the concerns regarding emerging technology. It further includes research ensembles promoting cross-disciplinary research teams, including engineers, technology scientists, and social scientists, to develop a perspective exchange. To get the empirical impact of the research, innovation labs will foster nanotechnology products designed to address the existing societal problems and, finally, influence the technology policy (Guston, 2010). The anticipatory approach research on the governance of AI could take a similar operationalization model.

However, it is crucial to understand that the anticipatory approach does not take control of the future of technological developments but recognizes the possible alternatives. Literature establishes that this approach brings in democratic values into the decision-making of technological advancements, so that it results in a better social life (Guston, 2013). However, it is well known that democracy is not purely in existence. In a country, if there has to be a real deliberation, only urban spaces can be chosen, and even their participants would be limited. In the case of technological governance, the deliberations would be with the representatives of societies. That means public participation involves academics, NGOs, bureaucracies, and scientists. Deliberation on the impacts of AI on society would need expert-led

groups along with the opinion of the general public. However, considering the complexity of AI, general public opinion would take less weight while considering the participatory models.

However, these approaches are criticized, saying that the method would involve researchers close to AI laboratories in practice and carry hubris of the latter. Some argue that the anticipatory governance model is the same as futurology studies (Guston, 2013, p. 231). Even though the criticism is valid, anticipatory governance as a method considers the future alternatives but does not involve prediction, forecast, or steering towards a restrictive alternative, as found in the futurology studies. It helps to train the systems for the uncertainties. It is always better to serve society with known or anticipated consequences rather than uncertainties of emerging technological impacts. Moreover, the significant difference between futurology studies and anticipatory governance is that the former shapes the public's thinking through its policies and narratives. At the same time, the latter analyzes the risk of technology in order to improve the efficiency of the governance (here the usage of technology).

Extensive usage of this method in drafting the policy for technology governance is found in the US during human genome initiative research. As a branch of Science & Technology Studies (STS) research, it has gained momentum in the early 2000s when Bill Clinton's administration provided \$13 million to research on the impact of nanotechnology on American society and how to pave the best path forward (Guston, 2013). This method is also used as a tool in assessing the climate change impact (Quay, 2010).

In a doctoral thesis submitted by Miles Brundage to Arizona State University in 2019, it is established that even though there are researchers broadly in the areas of Ethics, FAT Issues (Fairness, Accountability, and Trust), Control problem, and reliability. Anticipatory methods in AI governance lack coherence in bringing inclusion,

reflexivity, and responsiveness. The necessity to have anticipatory research on AI governance espoused to be mainly because of its nature of being a general-purpose technology, unequal access to the AI developments to the researchers, and its immense scalability, which would result in the concentration of economic power in the hands of few. It was found that AI anticipatory research encounters the problem of lack of awareness of the diverse views regarding the impact of AI on society (Brundage 2019, 54). Second is its nature of anticipatory future scenarios. Unlike other technological governance models, AI does not have any past data or experience to compare. All the alternative futures have to be constructed speculatively. Without emphasizing the term of anticipatory governance, OECD's technological governance espouses the Guston's anticipatory method in providing an opportunity to work as productively and practically as possible within the so-called Collingridge Dilemma³ (OECD). They claim to produce AI, which is in line with human values and democracy.

9. CONSIDERATION OF EITHER METHODS

It is established that the adoption of AI into daily societal activities brings advantages to the human society (Anderson, 2018) and Jurgen Schmidhuber (2023) opines that AI is inevitable in the social activities and soon becomes ubiquitous. It becomes necessary to undertake anticipatory research to tackle the uncertainty caused by AI. As discussed through out the paper, research using the anticipatory method can arrive from two different theoretical standpoints. One is systems theory and the other is Actor – Network theory. Luhmann's systems theory has its epistemological anchor in the traditional sociology and ANT of Latour deviates from the traditional sociology in understanding the society and technology's impact on it. Both

3 It is a dilemma of governance models emerged because of the unequal rate of change among the technological advancements and social changes. There is a confusion between the - ease of changes being made to the society and governance during the early stages of technology and the inability to change when necessary- (after the ubiquity).

approaches have their own advantages and disadvantages. The researcher could opt for either depending upon the requirement. If the research is for policy-making and requires immediate solutions, the system's theory would suffice. If a thick description of the AI's impact on society is desired along with a nuanced understanding of its impact on society, then ANT would be the option.

Nevertheless, if a regulatory policy or legal framework has to be designed for AI, a government's possible regulation would be to set up an independent regulatory authority such as TRAI or SEBI but with a more inclusive board (multi-stakeholder approach) (Matthew, 2016). As AI systems are discrete, any agency formed must be coordinated internationally. The latter proves to be a Himalayan task as there are no such institutions. Setting up strict lab rules also would not work as such legislation would lead to strong government decapitating democracy within technological innovations. In these scenarios, prior understanding of the impact of AI on the society using second-order observations will provide an appropriate assessment. In order to realize it, multi-disciplinary research would become a desideratum, and it can be realized using the anticipatory governance method. Subsequently, a legal framework can be drafted with all the stakeholders studied.

It is not challenging to opt ANT when the objective of the research is to regulate AI design or algorithms. Regulatory agencies have no way to regulate or test whether the AI system is in congruence with the law. This is because, how can the algorithm be tested? We can only be sure if it provides an accurate or desired output according to the testing environment. If it has to be tested with all the variables, it has to be deployed. Such problems require contextual miasma of causal relations between AI and society's fundamentals, and it is possible to arrive at such regulatory design with the ANT approach. This approach asks to re-construct the understanding of society and its perception of AI. It is more like ethnographic research.

10. ANTICIPATORY RESEARCH – UNDERSTANDING HATE SPEECH REPORTAGE

The proliferation of hate speech on the internet has become a pressing concern in today's digital age. News media, as a primary source of information for many individuals, plays a crucial role in shaping public discourse. To comprehend the phenomenon of hate speech content and reportage in news media, an anticipatory research method incorporating two theoretical approaches, Luhmann's social systems theory and Actor-Network Theory (ANT) in conducting anticipatory governance research, can provide valuable insights. This paper focused on anticipatory research in the context of AI governance, using two theoretical approaches: Luhmann's social systems theory and Actor-Network Theory (ANT). The case study chosen for analysis is the understanding of online reportage of hate speech. By examining how each approach influences the analysis of hate speech reportage, we can gain valuable insights into the anticipatory governance of AI in addressing this critical issue.

The proposed anticipatory research approach has practical implications for addressing hate speech in news media. Insights gained from this research can inform the development of targeted interventions, policies, and practices to mitigate the spread of hate speech. It can help identify leverage points within social systems and actor-networks to promote responsible journalism, ethical reporting, and inclusive online environments. By understanding the systemic factors that contribute to hate speech content, stakeholders can work towards designing effective strategies for prevention, moderation, and counter-narratives that foster a more tolerant and inclusive online news media landscape.

Using Luhmann's Social Systems Theory for Analysis of Hate Speech

When applying Luhmann's social systems theory to the understanding of hate speech reportage, the analysis takes a systemic perspective.

This approach emphasizes the examination of hate speech as a phenomenon within the broader social systems, focusing on the communication codes, norms, and structures involved. The analysis encompasses the following aspects:

1. **Societal Dynamics:** Luhmann's theory helps uncover the underlying social dynamics contributing to hate speech reportage. It examines the social context, power structures, and social inequalities that influence the production, dissemination, and reception of hate speech in the media.
2. **Role of Media Systems:** The theory sheds light on the role of media systems in amplifying hate speech. It explores how media organizations, journalistic practices, and editorial decisions influence the reporting and visibility of hate speech.
3. **Policy Implications:** Luhmann's social systems theory aids in identifying areas within the media system where interventions and policy changes can be implemented. It highlights the importance of responsible journalism, ethical reporting practices, and creating inclusive media environments to counter hate speech.

Using Actor-Network Theory (ANT) for Analysis

When employing ANT to understand hate speech reportage, the analysis focuses on the network of actors involved in the production, dissemination, and governance of hate speech. This approach explores the following aspects:

1. **Actor-Network Mapping:** ANT facilitates mapping the actors involved in hate speech reportage, including individuals, media organizations, algorithms, and online platforms. It examines how these actors interact and shape the production and visibility of hate speech.
2. **Technological Factors:** ANT recognizes the role of AI algorithms and content moderation technologies in hate speech reportage. It investigates how these technological components influence the detection, removal, or amplification of hate speech.

3. **Emergent Dynamics:** ANT allows for the identification of emergent properties and dynamics within the actor-networks surrounding hate speech. It explores the influence of non-human actors, such as AI systems, and their interactions with human actors in shaping hate speech reportage.

Impact on Analysis: The choice between Luhmann's social systems theory and ANT significantly influences the analysis of hate speech reportage in the following ways:

1. **Luhmann's Approach:** Using Luhmann's theory emphasizes the systemic aspects, focusing on the broader social context, power dynamics, and policy implications. It provides a comprehensive understanding of hate speech within the media system, highlighting the importance of social structures and norms.
2. **ANT Approach:** Employing ANT emphasizes the networked nature of hate speech, recognizing the role of technology and the interactions between actors. It offers insights into emergent properties, technological influences, and the agency of both human and non-human actors.

However, these methods have disadvantages. When examining the understanding of online hate speech reportage and the governance of artificial intelligence (AI), researchers can choose to utilize either Luhmann's social systems theory or Actor-Network Theory (ANT) separately. Below is a brief on the disadvantages of each approach:

Using Luhmann's Social Systems Theory

Disadvantages:

1. **Technological Gap:** Luhmann's social systems theory does not explicitly address the technological aspects of hate speech reportage and the governance of AI. It may overlook the specific role of AI algorithms, platforms, and content moderation technologies, which are critical in understanding and addressing online hate speech.

- 2. Complexity:** Luhmann's theory can be complex and may require a deep understanding of its concepts and terminology. Researchers not well-versed in sociological perspectives or the theory itself may face challenges in applying it effectively. This is also the major disadvantage in developing a governance structure within which AI algorithm is developed to track and understand the hate speech reportage.
- 3. Limited Actor Analysis:** This approach may place less emphasis on individual actors and their roles within the networks of hate speech reportage. It primarily focuses on systemic dynamics, potentially missing the individual agency and contributions to the production and dissemination of hate speech. Further, it misses out on how AI-generated content becomes the agency in changing the societal status-quo.

Using Actor-Network Theory (ANT)

Disadvantages:

- 1. Narrow Perspective:** ANT's focus on actor-networks may limit the analysis to specific relationships and interactions, potentially overlooking broader social and systemic factors contributing to hate speech. It may not provide a comprehensive understanding of the larger societal context and power dynamics surrounding hate speech reportage.
- 2. Complexity of Analysis:** ANT's methodology can be intricate, requiring researchers to meticulously trace and analyze the relationships between actors, objects, and technologies. This level of detail may present challenges, especially when studying large-scale actor-networks involving AI systems and complex online platforms.
- 3. Individual Actor Bias:** ANT's approach may diminish the agency and accountability of individual actors involved in hate speech reportage. It may not fully address the psychological, ideological,

and socio-cultural factors that motivate individuals to engage in hate speech.

11. CONCLUSION

The choice between Luhmann's social systems theory and ANT in analyzing hate speech reportage within the context of anticipatory governance of AI brings distinct perspectives to the analysis. Luhmann's theory focuses on systemic dynamics, social structures, and policy implications, while ANT emphasizes actor-networks, technological factors, and emergent dynamics. By considering each approach, researchers can gain a more comprehensive understanding of hate speech reportage and inform anticipatory governance strategies to effectively address this issue in the age of AI.

Anticipatory research is being carried out on AI in the US, but it is seldom heard in other countries like India. Given the increasing prevalence of hate speech online and the rapid development of AI technologies, understanding their intersection and implications for hate speech reportage is crucial.

Conclusively, conducting research on the anticipatory governance of AI and its influence on hate speech reportage in India is of utmost importance for several reasons:

1. **Addressing Hate Speech Challenges:** India, like many other countries, faces challenges related to hate speech in online reportage. Conducting research helps in understanding the underlying causes, dynamics, and impact of hate speech, leading to effective strategies for its prevention, mitigation, and regulation.
2. **Policy Development:** Informed research provides evidence-based insights for policymakers and stakeholders to develop comprehensive policies and regulations related to hate speech and AI governance. It helps in shaping legal frameworks, content moderation guidelines, and ethical practices in the online media space.

3. **Protecting Democratic Values:** Hate speech poses a threat to democratic values such as inclusivity, diversity, and freedom of expression. By examining the role of AI in hate speech reportage, researchers can contribute to the protection of these values and ensure that online platforms promote responsible and ethical reporting.
4. **Social Cohesion and Public Safety:** Hate speech has real-life consequences, leading to social divisions, conflicts, and even violence. Conducting research in India allows for a better understanding of how AI-enabled hate speech impacts social cohesion and public safety, leading to targeted interventions and prevention measures.
5. **Technological Advancement:** As India continues to witness rapid technological advancements and increased digital penetration, understanding the implications of AI on hate speech reportage becomes essential. Research can help identify the ethical considerations, algorithmic biases, and technical challenges associated with AI systems in the context of hate speech.

In conclusion, conducting research on the anticipatory governance of AI and its impact on hate speech reportage in India is crucial for addressing societal challenges, informing policy development, safeguarding democratic values, promoting social cohesion, and ensuring responsible technological advancements. It provides a valuable opportunity to shape the digital landscape in a way that fosters inclusivity, respect, and ethical reporting practices while leveraging the benefits of AI technologies.

The following are the possible (limited) future research questions that can emanate from this working paper:

1. How can anticipatory governance models be effectively applied in the design and deployment of Artificial Intelligence systems to ensure the preservation of intended societal changes?

2. What are the potential socio-economic imageries created by the adoption of Artificial Intelligence systems, and how can they be managed to avoid the objectification of societies?
3. How can Luhmann's System's theory be integrated into anticipatory governance models to enhance the assessment of risks associated with Artificial Intelligence?
4. What insights can be gained from Latour's Actor-Network Theory (ANT) in the context of anticipatory approaches to AI risk assessment?
5. How can the application of anticipatory research models, incorporating Luhmann's System's theory and Latour's ANT, contribute to a better understanding of hate speech in online reportage?
6. What are the key considerations and challenges in adopting either Luhmann's System's theory or Latour's ANT framework for conducting anticipatory research, and how can researchers effectively navigate these frameworks based on specific research requirements?
7. How do different anticipatory governance models impact the ethical dimensions of AI development and deployment, and what strategies can be employed to ensure responsible and accountable practices?
8. How can anticipatory research models be adapted and applied to other domains beyond hate speech, such as privacy concerns, algorithmic bias, or autonomous vehicles?
9. How can Artificial Intelligence systems be effectively utilized to detect and combat hate speech in online platforms, while also considering the ethical implications of automated content moderation?
10. What are the underlying socio-cultural factors that contribute to the prevalence of hate speech online, and how can AI technologies be leveraged to address these root causes?

11. How can predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms be employed to identify patterns and trends in hate speech, allowing for proactive intervention and prevention measures?
12. What are the potential biases and limitations of using AI for hate speech detection, and how can these challenges be addressed to ensure fair and accurate outcomes?
13. How can interdisciplinary approaches, combining linguistic analysis, social psychology, and AI, contribute to a comprehensive understanding of hate speech and the development of effective countermeasures?
14. What are the potential impacts of hate speech on marginalized communities, and how can AI be utilized to empower and protect these communities in online spaces?
15. How can AI-based hate speech detection systems be designed to adapt and evolve in response to emerging forms of hate speech and evolving language patterns?
16. What are the legal and regulatory challenges associated with combating hate speech through AI, and what policy frameworks can be implemented to ensure responsible and accountable use of these technologies?
17. How do cultural and regional differences influence the interpretation and detection of hate speech, and how can AI systems be trained to account for these variations?
18. How can the collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and technology companies be strengthened to effectively address the challenges posed by hate speech and promote a safer online environment?

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KEY CONCEPTS

DEFINITION OF AI

Defining AI poses challenges due to its multidisciplinary nature and evolving capabilities. The difficulty lies in capturing the complexity of AI, which encompasses various subfields like machine learning, natural language processing, and robotics. Additionally, the rapid advancements in AI technologies and their potential to surpass human capabilities make it challenging to provide a precise and static definition. Definitions often encompass AI's ability to simulate intelligent behavior, learn from data, and perform tasks traditionally requiring human intelligence, but ongoing debates and advancements continue to shape and refine these definitions.

RISK MANAGEMENT OF AI

The risk management of AI (Artificial Intelligence) involves identifying, assessing, and mitigating potential risks associated with the development, deployment, and use of AI technologies. This includes considerations of ethical, legal, social, and safety aspects, aiming to minimize negative consequences and maximize the benefits of AI systems in various domains.

ACTOR NETWORK THEORY

The ANT (Actor-Network Theory) is a theoretical framework in sociology and science studies that emphasizes the role of both human and non-human actors in shaping social systems and networks. It posits that actors, which can include people, technologies, organizations, and objects, are interconnected and form dynamic associations that influence social phenomena.

SOCIAL SYSTEMS THEORY

Social systems theory, developed by Niklas Luhmann, is a sociological perspective that views society as a complex system of interrelated parts.

It emphasizes the autonomy of social systems and focuses on the communication and interactions between system elements, such as individuals, organizations, and institutions, to understand how social order is maintained and evolves.

BRUNO LATOUR

Bruno Latour is a prominent French sociologist and philosopher known for his work in the field of science and technology studies. He is associated with Actor-Network Theory and has contributed to the understanding of how scientific knowledge is constructed, emphasizing the role of non-human actors and networks in shaping scientific practices and outcomes.

NIKLAS LUHMANN

Niklas Luhmann (1927-1998) was a prominent German sociologist and one of the most influential social theorists of the 20th century. He is known for his development of social systems theory, which has had a significant impact on various disciplines such as sociology, communication studies, and organization theory.

SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND SOCIETY

Science, Technology, and Society (STS) is an interdisciplinary field of study that explores the complex relationships between science, technology, and society. It examines how scientific and technological advancements impact social, cultural, political, and economic dimensions of society, as well as how social factors influence the development and use of science and technology.

ANTICIPATORY GOVERNANCE RESEARCH

Anticipatory governance research is an interdisciplinary field that focuses on the proactive and participatory management of emerging technologies and their potential societal impacts. It involves exploring and addressing the ethical, social, and environmental implications of new technologies before they become fully developed and widely

adopted. Anticipatory governance aims to integrate diverse perspectives, engage stakeholders, and foster collective decision-making processes to shape the development and deployment of technologies in a responsible and sustainable manner. By anticipating and addressing potential risks and challenges early on, anticipatory governance seeks to promote responsible innovation that aligns with societal values and priorities.

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Responsible research and innovation (RRI) is a framework and approach that emphasizes the ethical and societal dimensions of research and innovation processes. It calls for the active involvement of stakeholders, including researchers, industry, policymakers, civil society organizations, and citizens, in the co-design and co-production of research and innovation activities. RRI aims to ensure that scientific and technological advancements are conducted in a way that is responsive to societal needs, values, and concerns. It includes considerations of inclusiveness, gender equality, public engagement, ethics, sustainability, and open access to knowledge. Responsible research and innovation seeks to foster a more socially responsible and sustainable approach to research and innovation, promoting the alignment of scientific progress with societal goals and aspirations.

EX-ANTE RESEARCH ON AI

Ex-ante research refers to studies conducted before the deployment and widespread adoption of AI systems. It aims to anticipate and evaluate the potential societal, economic, ethical, and legal impacts of AI technologies. This research involves conducting scenario analyses, risk assessments, and policy evaluations to inform decision-making processes and regulatory frameworks. Ex-ante research helps identify and address potential challenges, risks, and opportunities associated with AI, allowing for the development of informed strategies and measures to mitigate negative consequences and maximize positive outcomes.

EX-POST RESEARCH ON AI

Ex-post research focuses on assessing and analyzing the actual impacts of AI technologies that have already been implemented. It involves monitoring and evaluating the real-world effects of AI systems on various stakeholders, including individuals, organizations, and society as a whole. Ex-post research utilizes empirical data, case studies, and impact assessments to understand the outcomes, unintended consequences, and long-term effects of AI applications. This research provides valuable insights into the societal, economic, and ethical implications of AI, helping policymakers, researchers, and practitioners refine their understanding, adjust policies, and develop informed strategies for responsible and beneficial AI development and deployment.

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY

Social psychology is a scientific discipline that explores how individuals' thoughts, feelings, and behaviours are influenced by social interactions and the social environment. It examines various aspects of human behaviour, including attitudes, social perception, conformity, prejudice, group dynamics, and interpersonal relationships. Social psychologists study the cognitive and emotional processes that shape our interactions with others and how these interactions impact our beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours. By understanding the underlying psychological mechanisms, social psychology seeks to shed light on the complex dynamics of human social behaviour and provide insights into individual and collective processes.

NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a subfield of artificial intelligence that focuses on the interaction between computers and human language. It involves the development of computational algorithms and models that enable computers to understand, analyze, and generate natural language. NLP encompasses a range of tasks, including text

classification, sentiment analysis, machine translation, information extraction, and question answering. Through techniques such as machine learning, statistical modeling, and linguistic analysis, NLP aims to enable computers to process and interpret human language in a way that is meaningful and useful for various applications, such as chatbots, information retrieval, and language understanding.

HATE SPEECH

Hate speech refers to any form of communication, whether written, spoken, or expressed through other means, that promotes, incites, or expresses discriminatory, offensive, or harmful views or actions towards individuals or groups based on attributes such as race, ethnicity, religion, gender, sexual orientation, or disability. Hate speech is characterized by its intent to degrade, demean, or incite violence or prejudice against individuals or communities. It often targets marginalized or vulnerable groups and can contribute to social divisions, prejudice, and discrimination. Recognizing and addressing hate speech is essential for promoting inclusivity, respect, and maintaining a harmonious and tolerant society.

AI BIAS

AI bias refers to the presence of systematic and unfair prejudices or discrimination in the outcomes or decisions made by artificial intelligence systems. Bias can arise in AI algorithms due to various factors, including biased training data, flawed model design, or inherent biases in the data sources. AI bias can result in discriminatory outcomes, perpetuate existing social inequalities, or reinforce stereotypes. Addressing AI bias is crucial for ensuring fairness, accountability, and ethical use of artificial intelligence technologies. It involves careful data collection and preprocessing, algorithmic transparency and explainability, and ongoing monitoring and evaluation of AI systems to mitigate biases and promote unbiased decision-making.

LATENT DIRICHLET ALLOCATION (LDA)

LDA is a method for discovering main topics in a collection of documents. It assumes each document is a mix of topics, and each topic is a collection of words. By analyzing word patterns, LDA uncovers the underlying topics, enabling efficient analysis of large text datasets without reading every document.

NAMED ENTITY RECOGNITION (NER)

NER, or Named Entity Recognition, is a technique that identifies and categorizes named entities in text, such as names of people, organizations, locations, dates, and more. By recognizing and tagging these entities, NER helps extract meaningful information from unstructured text, enabling applications like information retrieval, question answering, and text summarization.

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CDPP - RESEARCH TEAM

1. **Amitabh Kundu** has been chairperson of the Post-Sachar Evaluation Committee set up by Ministry of Minority Affairs.
2. **Soma Wadhwa** is a development studies researcher, with extensive experience as a media professional. She is a Senior Research Fellow at CDPP.
3. **Nahia Hussain** is Vice President (Policy Affairs) at CDPP, has worked on diverse issues like Gender Rights, Sustainability, Foreign Policy, and Criminal Justice.
4. **Venkatanarayana Motkuri** is associate Professor and Coordinator of Research Cell on Education (RSEPPG) at Centre for Economics and Social Studies (CESS), Hyderabad.
5. **Anjana Divakar** is the Managing Editor, Publications and a Research Associate at CDPP.
6. **Arun Teja Polcumpally** is an Associate Fellow at CDPP, an experienced researcher and technology policy analyst adept in qualitative and quantitative methods.
7. **Syed Moin Afroz** is Lead Graphic Designer at CDPP. He has been a part of the design industry for a decade now.
8. **Apoorva Ramachandra** is a research associate at CDPP. She has Masters in Economics from Jindal School of Government and Public Policy.
9. **Moumita Barman** is a Research Associate at CDPP. She has a Master's degree in Public Policy and Governance from the Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Hyderabad.
10. **Amir Ullah Khan** is Research Director at CDPP and a Development Economist. He teaches at ISB, IIFT, NALSAR, MCRHRDI and TISS.
11. **Mohd. Yaqoob Quraishi** is Manager (Operations and Finance) at CDPP. He has a degree of B.Com from Osmania University.

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CENTRE FOR DEVELOPMENT POLICY AND PRACTICE

10-3-303, 3rd Floor, Serene Heights, Masab Tank, Hyderabad - 500 028, T.S., India
info@cdpp.co.in | www.cdpp.co.in | 040 - 3516 4255 | +91 93915 81698